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Accessibility of ICT tools for Digital Agricultural Education in National Education Policy-2020

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Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are defined as all digital devices, tools, content, resources, forums, and services, as well as those that can be converted into or delivered through digital forms that can be deployed to achieve the goals of teaching and learning, improving access to and reach of resources and educational system management. These will include not only computer hardware and software applications, but also interactive digital content, internet and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web-based content repositories, interactive forums and learning management systems. Different ICT tools are stated to help improve access to education, enhance educational quality, strengthen the relevance of education to the increasingly digital workplace and help transform teaching and learning into an engaging, active process related to real life when utilized effectively. The integration of ICT into educational systems, on the other hand, ranges from the basic use of technology to help instruction (e.g., power point presentations) to the delivery of whole courses or programmes using ICT (e.g., MOOCs). However, students' ICT ownership, access, abilities, and amount and kind of use are all important factors in incorporating ICTs into their education. Desktop computers, projectors, and photocopiers are some examples of ICT resources. If these resources are not available in Institutions, it can prevent effective use of ICT in classrooms. The study conducted in UAS, Dharwad regarding accessibility of faculty and students to various ICT tools. Study revealed that (50%) faculty were have medium level access to various ICT tools followed by (30%) and (20%) high level and low level accessibility respectively. In case of students also, medium level access to ICT tools were more (40%) followed by low (36%) and high level (24%) accessibility respectively. So there is ample scope for adopting ICTs in teaching and learning on farm Universities under NEP-2020.

Accessibility and possession of ICT tools for Digital Agricultural Education in National Education Policy-2020

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Introduction

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are defined as all digital devices, tools, content, resources, forums, and services, as well as those that can be converted into or delivered through digital forms that can be deployed to achieve the goals of teaching and learning, improving access to and reach of resources and educational system management. These will include not only computer hardware and software applications, but also interactive digital content, internet and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web-based content repositories, interactive forums and learning management systems. Different ICT tools are stated to help improve access to education, enhance educational quality, strengthen the relevance of education to the increasingly digital workplace and help transform teaching and learning into an engaging, active process related to real life when utilized effectively. The integration of ICT into educational systems, on the other hand, ranges from the basic use of technology to help instruction (e.g., power point presentations) to the delivery of whole courses or programmes using ICT (e.g., MOOCs). However, students; ICT ownership, access, abilities, and amount and kind of use are all important factors in incorporating ICTs into their education. Desktop computers, projectors, and photocopiers are some examples of ICT resources. If these resources are not available in Institutions, it can prevent effective use of ICT in classrooms.

Objective

•To know the accessibility and possession of ICT tools of teachers and students.

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted during November 2021 to To know the accessibility and possession of ICT tools of teachers and students.

The samples for the study were 100 faculty members and 150 students from all colleges of University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad. Thus the total samples for the study were 250 faculty members and students.

Information was collected through personal interview using the structured schedule developed for the study.

Results and Discussion

It becomes clearly evident from Table-1, that (100.00%) teachers were having accessibility and possession of smart phone/ Mobile, Laptop, desk top Computer followed by pen drive (96.00%) and Television (88.00%) access in their own and by the department respectively. With respect to the students Table -2 indicate that majority of the students having accessibility and possession of smart phone/ mobile access (98.67.00%) followed by the Pen drive (69.33.00%), laptop (66.00%), desktop computer and camera access (29.33%) in their own and by the department respectively.

Table-1: Accessibility and possession of ICT tools of teachers

n= 100

SI.No	ICT tools	Accessible		Not Accessible	
		F	%	F	%
1	Smart Phone/ Mobile	100	100.00	0	0.00
2	Laptop	100	100.00	0	0.00
3	Pen drive	96	96.00	4	4.00
4	Desk top Computer	100	100.00	0	0.00
5	Radio	65	65.00	35	35.00
6	Television	88	88.00	12	12.00
7	Tablet	41	41.00	59	59.00
8	Camera	78	78.00	22	22.00
9	Web camera	82	82.00	18	18.00
10	Printer	86	86.00	14	14.00
11	Scanner	84	84.00	16	16.00
12	LCD Projector	87	87.00	13	13.00
13	External Hard disk	73	73.00	27	27.00
14	GPS device	40	40.00	60	60.00

Table-2 Accessibility and possession of ICT tools of students

n= 150

SI.No	ICT tools	Accessible		Not Accessible	
		F	%	F	%
1	Smart Phone/ Mobile	148	98.67	2	1.33
2	Desktop computer	44	29.33	106	70.67
3	Laptop	99	66.00	51	34.00
4	Printer	22	14.67	128	85.33
5	Radio	31	20.67	119	79.33
6	Camera	44	29.33	106	70.67
7	Tablet	39	26.00	111	74.00
8	Web camera	29	19.33	121	80.67
9	Pen drive	104	69.33	46	30.67
10	External Hard disk	34	22.67	116	77.33

Conclusion

It becomes clearly evident that (100.00%) teachers were having accessibility of smart phone/ Mobile, laptop, desk top Computer followed by pen drive (96.00%) and television (88.00%) access in their own and by the department respectively. With respect to the students majority of the students having accessibility of smart phone/ mobile access (98.67.00%) followed by the pen drive (69.33.00%), laptop (66.00%), desktop computer and camera access (29.33%) in their own and by the department respectively.